

DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ANNOTATION

The article analyzes trends in the socio-economic life of the society as a result of the development of the digital economy. The digital economy is formed due to the improvement of the means of production with a new important element - an automated (digital) control unit. This has led to significant changes in people's economic activities.

Key words: digital economy, labor tools, economic activity, goal setting, qualification.

Enter.

The implementation of electronic government elements and support of the digital economy have a strong place in Uzbekistan's near-term development plan. First of all, this concerns the tasks of further increasing the share of electronic document exchange and gradually transferring a certain part of state services to electronic form through State Service Centers. Telecommunications infrastructure plays an important role in this process.

The main part

Interest in the digital economy has grown significantly due to significant changes in society and the economy. Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals to reduce costs by minimizing personal communication with customers, partners, and government organizations, as well as making communication faster and easier. The result is a digital or electronic economy based on network resources.

The word "digitalization" is actually a new term, which refers to the involvement of IT solutions in the process of innovative management and administration, and as a result, the use of information technologies in all systems, from Internet of Things to e-government. .

The main source of the digital segment of the economy is the growth of the transactional sector. In developed countries, this indicator makes up more than 70 percent of GDP and combines public administration, consulting and information services, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as services (utility, personal and social).

The higher the diversification and dynamics of the economy, the greater the circulation of unique information inside and outside the country, and the greater the information traffic within national economies. Therefore, the digital economy

develops rapidly in markets where the number of participants is large and IT services are widespread.

In particular, it creates unlimited convenience for transport, trade, logistics and similar industries that actively work with the Internet. According to some researchers, the share of the electronic segment in them is close to 10% of the GDP and provides employment for 4% of the population. Most importantly, these indicators will grow steadily.

Undoubtedly, the effectiveness of the digital economy is influenced not only by the coverage of information technologies and the availability of infrastructure, but also by standard economic criteria such as the business environment, human capital, and successful management instruments. Therefore, economic development relies on them, which means that these criteria are as important as before in the development of the digital economy.

The digital economy is being created before our eyes

Today, old and new companies that use IT tools to create new services and business models around the world are creating strong competition for companies that are leaders in most industries.

According to forecasts, in the coming years, the macro-economy is expected to be strongly dependent on manufacturers relying on the criteria of "lean production", additive, nano and biotechnology. In this regard, the volume of information considered necessary for rational management will also increase, and the structure of production and civil communication, business and government bodies will undergo serious changes.

The following are indicated as the main conditions and factors for gradually entering the path of social and economic development:

- implementation of electronic government and digital city concepts due to informatization and integration of public administration bodies and municipal services;

- mass production of products of the new technological generation (such as driverless cars, etc.);

- implementation of ideas related to the construction of "smart" and ecological houses using unique decoration and building materials;

- wide promotion of alternative forms of employment through outsourcing, self-employment, etc.;

- creating professional networks that serve to search for workers-freelancers to perform certain tasks.

All of the above allows businesses to reduce costs with the help of modern platforms that integrate goods and electronic services in production and management. First of all, this issue concerns the integration of service orders, joint

use of resources, selection of counterparties, conduct of electronic trade, payments and others.

The technological digital environment is an "aquarium" in which legal entities and individuals establish a completely new dialogue for collaborative activities. Information technologies provide an opportunity for enterprises to adopt a completely new, faster pace of work and to diversify the form of services and products. In addition, researchers are also talking about the introduction of short shelf life products into the market.

When it comes to the service industry, information technology solves many daily tasks, making large-scale operations faster, cheaper, more convenient, and without intermediaries.

E-commerce, internet banking and other such modern directions are developing day by day. As a result, automated network services (such as a quality website or mobile application) are taking the place of business intermediaries in many industries to increase revenue.

As a result, business can significantly reduce the prices set for services, and in the macroeconomic direction, individual production and false employment indicators will increase. Also, directions such as crowdfunding and crowdsourcing are now included among new economic technologies.

According to economists, at the same time, as a result of such changes, the economy based on the practice of extracting additional value is changing to the economy of cooperation and sharing of interests ("sharing-economy"). This gives rise to hope that market competition will actively give way to mutually beneficial cooperation and cooperation, and at the same time, it will move from vertical communication to equal relations and complementary services.

According to estimates, this will be reflected in the increase in the number of services and the growth of the volume of electronic trade in services.

The economic importance of the digital sector

It is noted that digital technologies will dramatically change more than 50 percent of economy-related sectors. This vision is based on the fact that information technologies and digital platforms will dramatically change business models, eliminate intermediaries and optimize processes for their efficiency.

According to the calculations of the World Bank, a 10% increase in the number of high-speed Internet users can increase the annual GDP from 0.4% to 1.4%.

Also, the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP is considered to be about 20 percent annual growth (in developed countries, this indicator is around 7 percent) as an indicator of its importance.

In 2010, the Boston Consulting Group estimated the scale of digitalization at \$2.3 trillion (4.1 percent of GDP) for a group of 20 countries. If this trend continues, after 10-15 years the share of such an economy in the world GDP will approach 30-40%.

In developing economies, the IT sector employs about 1 percent of the population, and this sector creates more jobs than others. However, the rise of the IT sector is driving the creation of jobs in other sectors that are adopting new technologies (for every 1 new job created in the IT sector, there are 4.9 jobs in related sectors).

The digital economy boldly opens new horizons for entrepreneurs and self-employed people.

Often, the contribution to the development of the IT sector creates the basis for the development of the economy, the creation of new jobs, the emergence of new types of services for people and businesses, and the reduction of costs within the framework of e-government projects.

At the same time, the overall effect resulting from the implementation of information technologies turns out to be less effective than expected and not distributed in the same order.

Getting the most out of such investments requires a good understanding of how technology interacts with other factors, called "analog complements" in a World Bank report.

Among them:

regulatory legal framework that supports an active business environment and allows businesses and people to use digital economy technologies for competition and innovation, cost reduction, and improvement of living standards;

complete skills in the use of information technologies in business management and civil servants;

institutes (public and private) providing consulting services in the field of information technology use.

It is very difficult to enumerate the effects created by the digital economy, therefore, it is difficult to fully evaluate the connections that the access to electronic services and metadata provides to economic objects. Therefore, justifying the importance of investments in informatization, especially at the state level, is a rather difficult task. It is a self-evident phenomenon that it is impossible to always calculate gigabytes of information created in one or another field.

Digitization is a companion of new economic technologies

The communication models that have emerged as a result of the integration of information platforms give impetus to the emergence of new economic technologies (YIT).

IT is information that is integrated into a single technological platform to create, transmit, store and reflect information products (data, ideas and knowledge) that serve a purpose to organizational management systems and minimize the transaction costs spent on communication between economic agents. is a collection of new "customizable" tools and methods in all aspects of processing.

The main principles of IT:

creating radically new business models;

rational integration of various IT services and application of methods of their use in organizational and technological processes in the real economy sector; minimization of transaction costs and material resources used in production.

YIT develops in the current economic realities on the basis of digital technologies. Earlier, technologies related to production, trade, and finance have gradually improved, but now emerging ITs are focused on horizontal relations (self-organization and singularity), innovative entrepreneurship (self-development), information engineering (self-improvement) and serves as a basis for auto-formalization (automatic structure) of economic processes.

Data centers and modern IT platforms for information systematization and analytical processing form the true basis of IT. In this case, the development of the direction of providing services related to management consulting and business analysis is of great importance. New institutions, such as information and consulting services and state development agencies, serve as the organizational basis for improving the business environment.

Digital technologies and risks

The most active driver of the digital economy is the state. He is the main customer and consumer of the digital economy. For example, China spent about 9 billion dollars for these purposes. The Internet resource Alibaba, with a market capitalization of more than 210 billion dollars, proved that these investments were directed in the right direction.

A country that wants to get the maximum benefit from digitization should create and support the market for the necessary high-tech products. At the same time, while developing private applications for public administration, important sectors and enterprises in parallel, it is also important to keep the instruments that control the main platforms of the electronic economy in their tracks.

In particular, Japan lost the leading positions in the digital economy due to the fact that although it purchased technologies, it could not create its own manufacturing networks in this direction and could not maintain the level of technical developments at a consistently high level.

South Korea, on the other hand, invests 1% of the national budget in e-government and e-intermediation (for e-commerce activities and public procurement), generating 10-15 billion dollars annually and receiving income that covers costs 30-40 times. In particular, this result was achieved by organizing call centers in the public and private sectors, creating mobile applications and reengineering state-owned internet platforms.

Training of personnel working with information systems in state administration remains one of the important areas of this field. For example, in the 70s of the last century, in Belgium, special mobile groups of specialists (including teachers and students from specialized educational institutions) were organized to train employees of state bodies and configure systems directly for them at their workplaces. .

Another subtle aspect of the digital sphere is that the development of complex digital systems and their practical application requires a serious and detailed approach. It may seem strange to you, but often programming (in itself) is not really a sufficiently technological phenomenon. Therefore, the programmer who solves your tasks will act according to how he understands the task in many respects. Most important solutions are left unexplained in this process because each side assumes they are self-evident.

The accompanying documents related to the programs are sometimes compiled in a fragmented manner. As a result, in the process of working with the product, the customer loses control over the development that he ordered and paid for. In this case, the budget allocated to information projects does not provide for the costs of providing services, despite the fact that they are extremely important.

Summary

Because the digital economy covers the whole world, any government project related to information and digitization should be studied comprehensively and based on a single coding system, identifying economic and management related information.

The most important and at the same time the most difficult stage in the development of the digital economy is the simplification of the business environment and the maximum reduction of the costs of people and business communication with the state.

After that, it is required to establish an inter-organizational (multi-agent) dialogue within the framework of the public and private sectors of the parties.

The most important part of this process is digital economy platforms that move from "one-to-one" and "one-to-many" communication formula to "many-to-many" formula. Shifts in this area will automatically dramatically change the situation in the real sector of the economy (and stimulate structural reforms in these areas) through the development of consulting and technical organizations suitable for small and medium-sized businesses with state support, and help create conditions for an innovative economy. will give.

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